

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for ME1 (UniProt ID: P48163) for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence

Nicolas Curdy¹, Charles Alende^{†2}, Maryam Fotouhi^{†2}, Sara González Bolívar², Vincent Francis², Riham Ayoubi², Ivan Topisirovic¹ and Carl Laflamme^{2*}, NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group and ABIF consortium

[†] Authors contributed equally

¹ Department of Biochemistry, McIntyre Medical Building, McGill University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada

² Department of Neurology and Neurosurgery, Structural Genomics Consortium, The Montreal Neurological Institute, McGill University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada

* Corresponding author: carl.laflamme@mcgill.ca

Abstract

The ME1 (Malic Enzyme 1) protein plays a significant role in cellular metabolism, particularly in the conversion of malate to pyruvate, generating NADPH in the process. Here we have characterized ten ME1 commercial antibodies for western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While the use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

P48163, *ME1*, ME1, NADP-dependent malic enzyme, Malic enzyme 1, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

Malic Enzyme 1 (ME1), a key enzyme in cellular metabolism, catalyzes the oxidative decarboxylation of malate to pyruvate, producing NADPH in the process [1]. This enzyme is primarily involved in regulating cellular redox balance and energy metabolism, two crucial processes for maintaining cell homeostasis. In neurons, ME1 contributes to the regulation of oxidative stress, mitochondrial function, and synaptic activity, processes that are vital for learning, memory, and long-term potentiation (LTP) [2]. ME1 also acts as an oncogene (cancer-promoting factor) and is involved in various cancers, including oral, gastric, and breast cancers [3].

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data [4]. It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available renewable antibodies against the corresponding protein [4]. Here we characterized ten commercial ME1 antibodies, selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturers, for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence (also referred to as immunocytochemistry), enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of ME1 properties and function.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway [5] and in Table 4 of this data note [4].

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cells [6, 7]. The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million “TPM” + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off [8]. The HAP1 expresses the *ME1* transcript at $5.2 \log_2$ TPM+1. A *ME1* KO HAP1 cell line was obtained from Horizon Discovery (Table 1). Moreover, as seen on DepMap, the HAP1 does not carry mutations in the *ME1* that could affect antibody–epitope binding.

To screen all number of antibodies by western blot, WT and *ME1* KO (or ctrl and KD) protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with 10 *ME1* antibodies in parallel (Figure 1).

We then assessed the capability of all ten antibodies to capture ME1 from HAP1 protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. For the immunoblot step, a specific ME1 antibody identified previously (refer to Figure 1) was selected. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 2).

For immunofluorescence, ten antibodies were screened using a mosaic strategy. First, HAP1 WT and *ME1* KO cells were labelled with different fluorescent dyes in order to distinguish the two cell lines, and the ME1 antibodies were evaluated. Both WT and KO lines imaged in the same field of view to reduce staining, imaging and image analysis bias (Figure 3). Quantification of immunofluorescence intensity in hundreds of WT and KO cells was performed for each antibody tested, and the images presented in Figure 3 are representative of this analysis [4].

In conclusion, we have screened ten ME1 commercial antibodies by western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human HAP1 WT and *ME1* KO cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 4 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all three applications [8]. High-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect ME1 were identified in all applications. Researchers who wish to study ME1 in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available ME1 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners. We encourage readers to consult vendor documentation to identify the specific antigen each antibody is raised against, where such information is available.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in ME1, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. ME1 experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) [4]. Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

The cell lines, primary and secondary antibodies used in this study are listed in Table 1, 2, and 3, respectively. To ensure consistency with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations (where antibody concentrations are not disclosed), antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios rather than absolute concentrations. To facilitate proper citation and unambiguous identification, all cell lines and antibodies are referenced with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) [9, 10]. HAP1 KO clone corresponding to the *ME1* was generated with low passage cells. Single guide RNA was used to induce a 4 bp deletion in the *ME1* gene at exon 4 (guide sequence: TTATTACTATCCACGATCGA). All cell lines used in this study were regularly tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

Antibody screening by western blot

HAP1 WT and *ME1* KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of $\sim 0.2 \mu\text{g/ml}$ in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

HAP1 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 x *g* for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 1 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

HAP1 WT and *ME1* KO cells were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number C2925 and C34565). The nuclei were labelled with DAPI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. Number D3571) fluorescent stain. WT and KO cells were plated on 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator at 37°C, 5% CO₂. Cells were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) (VWR, cat. number 100503-917) in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Wisent, cat. number 311-010-CL). Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP151-500) for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum (Gibco, cat. number 16210-064) and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary ME1 antibodies overnight at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 µg/ml for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.95 water immersion objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification [11]. Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

Data availability

Underlying data

Zenodo: Dataset for the ME1 antibody screening study <[10.5281/zenodo.17402309](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17402309)>

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Synaptic Systems, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

Author contributions:

Vera Ruíz Moleón- Investigation

Riham Ayoubi-Investigation, Supervision, Writing – Original Draft Preparation

Maryam Fotouhi-Investigation

Charles Alende-Investigation

Vincent Francis- Writing – Review & Editing

Peter S. McPherson Roles- Supervised and Funding Acquisition

Carl Laflamme- Roles: Conceptualization, Funding Acquisition, Writing – Review & Editing

All authors reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC005910c001	CVCL_SX69	HAP1	<i>ME1</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the ME1 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab322401**	1109017-2	AB_3698262	recombinant mono	EPR28891-30	rabbit	0.54	Wb
ABclonal	A23068	5500037777	AB_3713256	polyclonal	-	rabbit	2.80	Wb
Abnova	H00004199-M01*	DA211-2A2	AB_540381	monoclonal	2A2	mouse	0.38	Wb
Abnova	H00004199-M03*	P1081-3H5	AB_2143826	monoclonal	3H5	mouse	1.00	Wb, IF
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP32794_P050	QC74013- 191031	AB_2047024	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP74638_P050	QC48039-42004	AB_3698301	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
GeneTex	GTX104122	44909	AB_1950905	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.94	Wb, IP, IF
GeneTex	GTX632188*	42037	AB_2888294	monoclonal	GT736	mouse	2.57	Wb, IF
GeneTex	GTX632189*	42037	AB_2888295	monoclonal	GT979	mouse	1.00	Wb, IF
GeneTex	GTX632190*	42037	AB_2888296	monoclonal	GT15611	mouse	1.00	Wb

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody, NA=not available

Table 3: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration (µg/µL)	Working concentration (µg/mL)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.05
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM001	AB_3068333	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.5
Abcam	Anti-mouse IgG for IP (HRP)	ab131368	AB_2895114	monoclonal	1.0	2.0
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 555-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR003	AB_3073507	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.5
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 555-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM003	AB_3068539	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.5

Table 4: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

Western blot			Immunoprecipitation			Immunofluorescence		
Successful antibody	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody	Successful antibody	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody	WT/KO cell mosaic	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody
WT KO	WT KO	WT KO	SM UB IP	SM UB IP	SM UB IP	WT	WT	WT
WT	WT	WT	SM	SM	SM	KO	KO	KO
KO	KO	KO	UB	UB	UB			
IP	IP	IP	IP	IP	IP			
kDa	kDa	kDa	kDa	kDa	kDa			
245-	245-	245-	245-	245-	245-			
135-	135-	135-	135-	135-	135-			
75-	75-	75-	75-	75-	75-			
48-	48-	48-	48-	48-	48-			
25-	25-	25-	25-	25-	25-			
11-	11-	11-	11-	11-	11-			
Target protein detected (arrowhead)	Target protein detected (arrowhead) among others	Target protein not detected	Target protein captured in the IP	Target protein captured in the IP	Target protein not captured in the IP	Target protein detected (white staining)	Target protein not detected	

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Figure 1: ME1 antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: ME1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 3: ME1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: ME1 antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of HAP1 WT and *ME1* KO were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated ME1 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab322401** at 1/1000; A23068 at 1/250; H00004199-M01* at 1/500; H00004199-M03* at 1/500; ARP32794 at 1/500; ARP74638 at 1/500; GTX104122 at 1/5000; GTX632188 *at 1/1000; GTX101089 at 1/1000; GTX632190* at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 64.1 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: ME1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

HAP1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 0.5 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated ME1 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the ME1 antibody H00004199-M03* used at 1/500. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=6% starting material; UB=6% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 3: ME1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

HAP1 WT and *ME1* KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio on coverslips. Cells were stained with the indicated ME1 antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (WT), red (antibody staining) and far-red (KO) channels was performed. Representative images of the blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. When an antibody was recommended for immunofluorescence by the supplier, we tested it at the recommended dilution. The rest of the antibodies were tested at 1 and 2 µg/ml, and the final concentration was selected based on the detection range of the microscope used and a quantitative analysis not shown here. Antibody dilutions used: ab322401** at 1/250; A23068 at 1/1000; H00004199-M01* at 1/400; H00004199-M03* at 1/500; ARP32794 at 1/250; ARP74638 at 1/250; GTX104122 at 1/1000; GTX632188*at 1/400; GTX101089 at 1/400; GTX632190*at 1/200. Bars = 10 µm. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.